

LOCALIZED MODULE IN PROMOTING PHILIPPINE-HILOT IN TEACHING WELLNESS MASSAGE AND THE STUDENT'S PERFORMANCE IN TLE 10: INPUT TO NEW DELIVERY MODES OF INSTRUCTION

SHIELA MASANGKAY AGUILA¹

DR. EDNA O. BRIONES²

ella_masangkay@yahoo.com¹

edna.briones@lspu.edu.ph²

Col. Lauro D. Dizon Memorial Integrated High School, Department of Education¹
Laguna State Polytechnic University, San Pablo City Campus, San Pablo Laguna, Philippines²

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to promote localized Philippine-Hilot in teaching Wellness Massage as a new delivery mode of instruction and its contribution on the improvement of students' performance in TLE 10. This is a descriptive correlational research which aimed to determine the effectiveness of instructional module among the 77 wellness massage students at Col. Lauro D. Dizon Memorial Integrated High School. The self-made questionnaire was used in this study and validated by experts in the field of wellness massage. The responses from the respondents were generated through online survey. The result was analyzed using mean, standard deviation and Pearson Product-Moment Coefficient (Pearson-r). The study revealed that the respondents were mostly 15 to 17 years of age. There were more male respondents. Most of the respondents have fathers that were employed and mothers that are unemployed or housewife. Most of the respondents have fathers and mothers who are high school graduates. Most of the respondent's family income is lower than Php 5,000. The result shows that majority of the students have an excellent level of performance with a grade of above 90 in both written and practical examinations. The results indicate that the majority of the respondents performed well in the test on localized module. There is significant relationship between the components and format of the module in wellness massage and students' performance in both written and practicum on the module. The hypothesis stating that the perception of the respondents on the components and format of the module in wellness massage in terms of objectives, learning content, activities and their performance is not significantly related to written examination and practicum is not sustained. The assessment tool, on the other hand, indicates no significant relationship in terms of written examination hence the hypothesis in this respect is sustained.

Keywords: localized module, module format, written examination, practicum